

TRENDS in Pediatric Palliative Care Research (TPPCR) 2026; Issue #04: Commentary on

Holland, C. et al.

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Abstract:

This TPPCR commentary discusses the 2026 paper by Holland, C. et al., Symptom management:

How can specialist pediatric palliative care teams help?, in the Archives of Disease in

Childhood: Education and Practice Edition.

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Through a brief, simple and descriptive clinical case study, Holland and collaborators from the Helen and Douglas House (UK) point out the important role of Specialists in Pediatric Palliative Care (SPPC). These specialists' roles include teaching the key principles of comprehensive symptom management among pediatric professionals outside the PPC community. This is a great need all over the world!

The authors illuminate the increasing “medical complexity” that pediatricians and other pediatric professionals are encountering in many settings. As a consequence, the generalized need for disseminated knowledge and competencies for comprehensive symptom management is expanding. This article highlights the importance that SPPC interface with local core providers and tertiary specialists to ensuring equitable access and support for patients and families.

With two simple vignettes, one with the case of a child with a severe neurological disease and another of an adolescent with advanced cancer, the authors describe the applicability of a comprehensive symptom management model, either for the diagnostic and analytical phase or for the multimodal treatment approach, for symptoms presented in children facing life limiting or threatening conditions (LLTC).

Authors highlight the importance of interdisciplinary approach to understand biological, psychosocial and spiritual determinants. This article considers exacerbating factors as well as multimodal treatment, both pharmacological and non-pharmacological management, using evidence-based and expert recommendations for symptom control and prescription.

Through the clinical examples, they show the applicability of this model to the following frequent problems: feed-related visceral symptoms, dystonia and neuropathic pain in children

with severe neurological impairment in different stages of disease trajectory and to breathlessness in children with cancer.

The authors also draw attention to challenges typically present in pediatric settings: the frequent co-existence of 3 symptoms, on average, in children with LLTC, becoming more frequent close to end of life; the heterogeneity in access to SPPC according to health care setting, locality or country; and difficulties related to medication administration, including medication refusal. What is helpful is that the authors include some advice regarding these situations, and note the availability of liquid medications suitable for children as one example.

As for recommendations, the authors also encourage empowering patients and families to actively participate in the decisions regarding quality of life. In addition, they note the importance of including SPPC, particularly when symptoms are complex or additional support for healthcare professionals, children or families is needed when navigating complex decision-making or changing illness trajectory.

From my perspective in Latin America, what I found interesting about this article is that it offers practical and simple ideas for addressing a global problem. There is a growing need for a PPC approach for the increasing number of children living with LLTC, and to address the worldwide scarcity and heterogeneity in accessing quality PPC. This increases the need to democratize both knowledge and PPC competencies. The article comes from the Helen and Douglas house, the birthplace of PPC. It shows that even in high income countries, it is unlikely that all children in need of PPC will be able to access professionals with advanced specialist training. This is even more pronounced for those living in medium or low-income countries, where most of the children in need of PPC live.

In our experience in a small Latin American country such as Uruguay, we understand that training enough interdisciplinary SPPC professionals will take much longer than suffering children can wait, therefore other strategies are necessary in the meantime.

That is why I agree with the authors that SPPC should be available for direct complex symptom management and support for families and professionals navigating complex decision-making processes. Critically, disseminating guidance and principles of comprehensive symptom management to non-SPPC professionals is helpful for those in charge of the children at shifts and in all clinical settings. Although it is not easy, we are strongly convinced that clinical care, education, research, and advocacy must be simultaneous tasks for leaders and specialists in PPC

In our opinion, this brief report is a nice example and hopefully a model for more literature by other colleagues from all over the world describing other specific clinical situations and challenges. As with this one, they might help to illuminate clinical management to many pediatric professionals who don't have the possibility of advanced PPC training, but do have the need to comprehensively address children suffering all over the world.